

A HYBRID DC-LG ALGORITHM FOR IMPROVING EFFICIENCY AND ACCURACY IN PREDICTIVE ANALYTICS

GAYATHRI.R¹ and Dr. RAJAVARMAN.V.N²

¹Research scholar, Department of Information Technology, Dr.MGR Educational and Research Institute, Chennai, Tamilnadu, India. ¹Email: gayathri.cse@drmgrdu.ac.in

²Professor, Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Dr.MGR Educational and Research Institute, Chennai, Tamilnadu, India. ²Email: rajavarman.vn@drmgrdu.ac.in

ABSTRACT

Cardiovascular diseases (CVD) have been the most usually taking place predominant situations impacting human fitness. CVDs may be prevented or managed with early detection, which can also additionally bring about decrease loss of life rates. Using gadget mastering algorithms to perceive threat variables is a promising method. We could need to provide a version that consists of many methodologies if you want to offer proper cardiac sickness prediction. To make certain the fulfilment of our proposed version, we hired green records collection, transformation methods and pre-processing to offer accurate records for the reason of schooling version. We analyzed a pooled dataset (Switzerland, Cleveland, Long Beach VA, and Stat log together with Hungarian). The proposed Hybrid Dc-LG algorithm is deployed to predict the heart disease. The prediction accuracy is compared with various other existing algorithms. To facilitate comparisons, the findings are offered individually. We can finish from the effects evaluation that our counselled version generated the most accuracy of 90%. Cardiovascular contamination has historically been taken into consideration the maximum severe and lethal sickness internal human body. Globally, the growing occurrence of cardiovascular ailments related to an excessive mortality charge poses a enormous threat and burden on healthcare systems. Men are much more likely to have cardiovascular problems than women, in particular in center or antique age [1], [2], nevertheless kids can increase similar fitness problems [3], [99].

Keywords: Decision tree, Outliers, Accuracy, Hybrid.

INTRODUCTION

According to WHO data, heart disease is to blame for one-third of all deaths globally each year. It is estimated that cardiovascular disease claims the lives of around 17.9 million people each year throughout the world [4], [5]. According to the European Cardiology Society (ESC), there are around 26 million people worldwide who have been diagnosed with cardiac illness, with an additional 3.6 million being diagnosed each year. In the first two years after diagnosis, around half of all patients with heart disease die, and heart disease treatment accounts for about 3% of total health-care spending [6]. To effectively predict heart illness, you'll need a slew of different tests. Improper forecasting may be the result of medical staff lacking sufficient expertise [7]. It may be difficult to diagnose cancer at an early stage [8]. The surgical treatment of heart disease is tough, and this is much truer in developing countries that lack medical professionals, diagnostic equipment, and other resources essential for accurate diagnosis and treatment of heart patients [9]. It would help avoid catastrophic heart attacks and improve patient safety if cardiac failure risk could be precisely assessed. Machine learning algorithms can indeed be effective at detecting diseases provided they are properly

taught with relevant data [11]. To compare prediction models, there are publicly available datasets on heart disease. Scientists can now build the most accurate prediction model possible by combining machine learning and artificial intelligence, which are both on the rise. Cardiovascular disease (CVD) mortality has been on the rise in both adults and children, according to recent studies. Pre-processing is necessary due to the lack of uniformity and duplication in publicly available clinical datasets. [12]. It's vital to pick meaningful characteristics that may be used in prediction models as risk factors. Care should be taken while picking features as well as machine learning techniques for building trustworthy prediction models [13]. When looking at risk factors for heart disease, it's crucial to include those that meet three criteria: they're present in most people, they have a significant impact independently on heart disease, and they're within our direct control or treatment to reduce our chances [14]. There are numerous chance elements or developments that researchers have included into all in their fashions pertaining to CVD prediction. Exercise-caused angina (exang), exercise-caused ST melancholy in comparison to rest (old peak), slope, the range of essential vessels colored through fluoroscopy (ca), coronary heart state, most coronary heart charge reached (thalach), negative nutrition, and own circle of relatives records are all elements that need to be considered. According to current studies, a prediction have to meet at the least 14 traits with the intention to be correct and dependable [20]. Current studies struggles to mix those functions with suitable gadget studying algorithms with the intention to create a correct prediction of coronary heart disease [21]. Machine studying algorithms which have been skilled on applicable datasets are the maximum successful [22]–[25]. Data mining, alleviation selection, and LASSO are all techniques that could assist put together the statistics for a greater correct prediction due to the fact the algorithms rely upon the consistency of the schooling and checking out statistics. The chance of sickness occurrence may be predicted using classifiers and hybrid models after identifying the relevant factors. Different methodologies have been used by researchers to construct classifiers and hybrid models. Insufficient datasets of medical, selection of features, implementation of machine learning algorithms, as well as a lack of in-depth analysis are among the problems that may block accurate cardiac illness prediction. These information gaps will be filled by our study in order to create a more accurate CVD prediction model. This study incorporates data from five different datasets, resulting in a larger final dataset.

Cardiovascular ailment may be efficiently managed with a mixture of life-style modifications, medication, and, in uncommon situations, surgery. With the proper therapy, the signs and symptoms of coronary heart ailment may be alleviated and the coronary heart's characteristic enhanced. Predicted effects may be utilised to keep away from and thereby decrease the price of surgical remedy and different high priced procedures.

The foremost intention of my studies may be to reliably be expecting the lifestyles of coronary heart ailment the usage of a restrained range of exams and features. Considered attributes function the foremost foundation for checking out and offer fairly dependable findings. Numerous different enter variables is probably used, however our goal is to forecast the threat of growing coronary heart ailment the usage of fewer and greater green features. Often, medical doctors make selections primarily based totally on their instinct and

experience, in place of at the knowledge-wealthy records blanketed with inside the records series and databases. These method consequences in unwanted biases, mistakes, and useless clinical expenses, all of that have a bad effect at the high-satisfactory of care provided to patients.

For the healthcare business, records mining have massive promise because it permits fitness establishments to systematically use records and analytics to discover inefficiencies and quality practises that decorate remedy and keep expenses. According to (Wurz & Takala, 2006), probabilities to decorate remedy whilst reducing expenses may account for as much as 30% of general healthcare spending. Data mining's fulfilment in enormously seen disciplines including e-commerce, marketing, and retail has led to its software in loads of different agencies and sectors. Healthcare is this sort of regions this is nonetheless coming across itself. Healthcare continues to be a "information-wealthy" yet "knowledge-poor" setting. Within healthcare systems, a plethora of records is to be had. However, there may be a dearth of suitable evaluation techniques for figuring out underlying hyperlinks and developments inside African genres' records.

Cardiovascular Diseases account for 31% of fatalities global every year (CVDs). While there are numerous clinical gear to be had available in the marketplace for predicting cardiac ailment, all of them be afflicted by massive flaws:

1. They are rather costly.
2. They are incapable of accurately calculating the risk of heart disease.

Machine learning may be a superior option for achieving high predictive accuracy for heart disorders. The primary aim is to develop a machine learning model capable of predicting whether or not a person has Heart Condition based on a combination of risk factors (parameters) defining the disease. To improve accuracy, four methods were analysed:

- Support Vector Machine (SVM)
- K-Nearest Neighbour Algorithm (KNN)
- Random Forest Classifier
- Hybrid Classifier Model

BACKGROUND AND BASICS

The heart is a critical organ for the healthy functioning of our bodies. According to a WHO report, cardiovascular diseases account for 31% of all fatalities globally each year (CVDs). Additionally, over 75% of these fatalities occur in low- and middle-income nations, including India. The primary difficulty is precisely predicting the presence of CVDs within the human body. The previous strategies have been ineffective in accurately predicting cardiac problems. Numerous medical equipment are available on the market for the prediction of heart disorders, but these instruments have several disadvantages, including their high cost and inefficiency in forecasting heart diseases[10].

Age, gender, blood pressure, cholesterol, blood sugar, and diabetes, as well as various lifestyle variables such as obesity, bad eating habits, insufficient physical activity, smoking, and alcohol use, are all key risk factors for heart disease. The majority of lifestyle risk factors are within our control. Medical science has made excellent use of technology breakthroughs over the last several decades to improve the quality of healthcare. These technological developments have paved the path for more precise illness detection and prognosis. Because machine learning is capable of analysing enormous volumes of data and recognising patterns and trends, it may be an excellent candidate for achieving high accuracy in predicting cardiac illnesses. Additionally, machine learning produces considerably more accurate and timely results. There are more soft computing techniques, such as Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), Deep Learning, Fuzzy Logic, Data Mining, and Genetic Algorithms, that can be used for heart disease prediction.

RESEARCH GAP

Feature selection as well as classical classification approaches has been the focus of most research in order to improve prediction accuracy. The accuracy of the model suffers because of missing data values (as they reduce the sample population inside the data, leading to an ineffective model). However, this issue has gotten little attention. In previous research aiming at improving accuracy, the problem of class imbalances (where another sample size about one level or class is much lower as compared to the study population in relation to different class/classes) was not well addressed. Prior to presenting any sort of classification method, it's critical to solve the problems of incomplete data and class imbalance.

Also, the dataset's properties have a substantial influence on the accuracy as well as complexity of computational nature of something like the process of machine learning, as well. As a result, selecting the proper subset of attributes for feature extraction is the fundamental goal of any machine learning process. The feature selection process as a whole appears to require marked enhancement to make sure the right subset of features is handpicked that contributes to dependable prediction with increased accuracy, even though researchers have also proposed different types of techniques of feature selection as well as algorithms of classification for just the datasets that are given. If you want to keep classifier processing complexity to a minimum, make sure your feature selection strategy extracts just those bits that are absolutely essential for making accurate predictions. Classification methods must also be effective if they are to boost accuracy.

Thus, a flexible Hybrid Dc-IG Algorithm that is applicable to a broad range of datasets, accounts for missing values/unbalanced classes, and delivers credible predictions (with few features and low computational cost) is uncommon in the literature.

METHODOLOGY

In this article, we suggest a unique Hybrid Dc-IG Algorithm for cardiovascular disease prediction. The purpose of this research is to demonstrate an accurate machine learning model capable of accurately identifying cardiovascular illnesses using clinical information from patients. The suggested strategy is comprised of the following steps: 1) Data preparation, which includes the elimination of outliers, the replacement of missing values, and the management of imbalance classes. [Alg 1 and 2] 2) Feature selection based on feature relevance. Following that, model training is carried out, and the trained model is utilised to generate predictions. Our primary goal is to get superior results with a smaller number of characteristics and a lower level of computational complexity. Now, we shall discuss our Hybrid Dc-IG Algorithm. Initially, the suggested Hybrid Dc-IG Algorithm performs data preparation. The data preparation stage largely involves the examination of the data for probable outliers. In a dataset, outlier is a sample that differs significantly from the average behaviour related to the dataset [30].

In data, more than 50 percent of large number of outliers is regarded as background noise, which has no bearing on data's usefulness and reduces a model's accuracy. Raveendrababu et al. [31] has stated that in order to remove outliers out from data helps get better outcomes, and they have provided several methods for doing so. With the use of Boxplot, our proposed Hybrid Dc-IG Algorithm removes outliers from the data. Summarizing five numerical values using boxplots is common. These five numerical values include: the minimum; Q1; Q2; Q3; and the highest. A box-like structure forms when all these five values are plotted; any value outside of the box is referred to be an outlier. Our proposed Hybrid Dc-IG Algorithm looks

for missing values after removing outliers. Missing values in datasets are common and might be caused by a faulty instrument or a clerical error. [32]. because there are fewer training examples available when the datasets involves missing values, as the model may indeed not be efficiently trained on it. Because of this, the model's accuracy has been lowered. As a result, the Hybrid Dc-IG Algorithm we propose replaces missing data with the attribute's mean value's mean value instead. Missing data is routinely replaced using the mean replacement approach, which is popular among scientists (e.g., Dodeen et al [33]). Over fitting is reduced since the training data may be retained without adding new information to the dataset. After pre-processing, feature selection is done by choosing any one of the feature selection algorithm where the less relevant features are removed. After which the data comes to the final stage, where the proposed method of Hybrid Dc-IG Algorithm would be to deal with predicting the disease by building the decision tree model rather than using entropy, but by using logistic regression less loss rate. Previously The Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique (SMOTE) is entirely based on Canopy as well as K-means clustering [34] addresses this issue. SMOTE enhances the representative sample related to the class which are in minority by identifying the k closest neighbour of the minority class in question. The sample size for the minority class is then increased by selecting one of several k nearest neighbours at random [35]. This method may be used forever to create an unlimited number of samples from the minority class. To increase reliability and reduce unpredictability, this technique generates samples that are remarkably identical to the original.

Our Hybrid Dc-IG Algorithm, on the other hand, uses ensemble classification and boosting to improve classification accuracy. By learning from its past results, the model becomes better at producing them going forward. Using a set of independent variables and the Logistic Regression approach, one may predict a categorical dependent variable's value. It's been widely used in health care to handle a wide range of forecasting problems.

PROPOSED ALGORITHM:

The Decision Tree approach is a well-known machine learning algorithm even though it is non-parametric. Whenever a particular attribute can easily be utilised to separate the data and help with judgement, it works well. [50].

The inputs used to create trees for training samples of data D have a high degree of randomness. Top-down recursion divide-and-conquer (DAC) is used to quickly and easily create these trees. On D, tree pruning is used to eliminate irrelevant samples.

$$\text{Entropy} = - \sum_{j=1}^m p_{ij} \log_2 p_{ij}$$

Algorithm 1

Decision Tree-Based Partition

Require: Input: D dataset - features with a target class

for $\forall$ features **do**

for Each sample **do**

Execute the Decision Tree algorithm

end for

Identify the feature space $f_1, f_2, \dots, f_x$ of dataset UCI.

end for

Obtain the total number of leaf nodes $l_1, l_2, l_3, \dots, l_n$ with its constraints

Split the dataset D into $d_1, d_2, d_3, \dots, d_n$ based on the leaf nodes constraints.

Output: Partition datasets $d_1, d_2, d_3, \dots, d_n$

Algorithm 2

Apply ML to Find Less Error Rate

Require: Input: Datasets with partition - $d_1, d_2, d_3, \dots, d_n$

for $\forall$ apply the rules **do**

On the dataset $R(d_1, d_2, d_3, \dots, d_n)$

end for

Classify the dataset based on the rules $C(R(d_1), R(d_2)$

$\dots, R(d_n)$)

Output: Classified datasets with rules $C(R(d_1), R(d_2)$

$\dots, R(d_n)$)

Algorithm 3

Feature Extraction Using Less Error Classifier

Require: Input: Classified datasets

$C(R(d_1), R(d_2), \dots, R(d_n))$

for A Find out min error rate from the input **do**

$\text{Min}(C(R(d_1), R(d_2), \dots, R(d_n)))$

end for

Find out max error rate from the classifier.

Output: Features with classified attributes $F(d_1, d_2, d_3,$

$\dots, d_n)$

Algorithm 4

Apply Classifier on Extracted Features

Apply the hybrid method based on the error rate

$$\sum_0^n F(n) = d + m_1x_1 + m_2x_2 + \dots + m_nx_n$$

$$\sum_0^n F(0) = \text{Gain} + \sum_0^n wix_i$$

DATASET

This dataset was used to demonstrate the applicability of our Hybrid Dc-IG Algorithm. There were three times as many rounds of data gathering as there were rounds of testing. In 1948, 5209 men and women between the ages of 30 and 62 were polled as part of the first round of the study. After the second round of screening was completed in 1971, a total of 5124 people were asked to submit to the same testing process again. These people were the offspring of the first wave of patricians. Eventually, the final cycle of data collection with the original cohort's

third generation ended in April 2002. The Framingham study gathered data on three generations of people: the original participants, their own children, and their grandchildren. The dataset includes all of this information. This improves the dataset's trustworthiness and guarantees that reliable predictions can be made from it. 4240 samples have been collected for this study; 644 of those are from class 1 (yes), while 3596 come from class 2. (No). Cardiovascular disease patients are represented by Class 1 samples, whereas healthy participants are represented by Class 2 samples. There are fifteen differentiating factors in this study. In addition to demographic and behavioural data, the dataset also includes medical history as well as current medical state, so it's a comprehensive resource. In order to generate CVD predictions, we propose a Hybrid Dc-IG Algorithm that takes use of these features. The properties of the dataset are summarised in Table 2.

Dataset

Patients' data from Cleveland, Hungary, Long Beach, and Switzerland comprise the Heart disease data collection. The merged dataset contains 14 characteristics and 916 samples, the majority of which include missing values. The following features are utilised in this section:

1. **age**: The patients age in years
2. **sex**: The patients gender(1=male; 0=female)
3. **cp**: Chest pain type, *Value 1: typical angina *Value 2: atypical angina *Value 3: non-anginal pain *Value 4: asymptomatic
4. **trestbps**: Resting blood pressure (in mm Hg on admission to the hospital)
5. **chol**: Serum cholesterol in mg/dl
6. **fb**: Fasting blood sugar > 120 mg/dl? (1=true; 0=false)
7. **restecg**: Resting electrocardiographic results *Value 0: normal *Value 1: having ST-T wave abnormality (T wave inversions and/or ST elevation or depression of > 0.05 mV) *Value 2: showing probable or definite left ventricular hypertrophy by Estes' criteria
8. **thalach**: Maximum heart rate achieved
9. **exang**: Chest pain(angina) after exercise? (1=yes; 0=no)
10. **thal**: Not described *Value 3=normal *Value 6=treated defect *Value 7=reversible defect
11. **num**: Target *Value 0: less than 50% narrowing of coronary arteries(no heart disease) *Value 1,2,3,4: >50% narrowing. The value indicates the stage of heart disease

Dataset creators,

1. Hungarian Institute of Cardiology, Budapest: Andras Janosi, M.D.
2. University Hospital, Zurich, Switzerland: William Steinbrunn, M.D.
3. University Hospital, Basel, Switzerland: Matthias Pfisterer, M.D.
4. V.A. Medical Center, Long Beach and Cleveland Clinic Foundation: Robert Detrano, M.D., Ph.D.

We describe a novel approach to utilise machine learning algorithms to discover important traits, which improves the reliability of cardiovascular disease forecasting. A variety of feature combinations and well-known classification methods are used to introduce the prediction model. By merging a hybrid decision tree with such a linear model, we can

construct a prediction model for cardiovascular disease that performs better and is 90% accurate. To begin, the machine learning approach uses pre-processing to prepare the data. Then, features are selected using the DT entropy, modelling performance is evaluated and improved accuracy is obtained. There are several attribute combinations to choose from; therefore the feature selection as well as modelling procedure is repeated.

Table 2: attributes of Framingham dataset.

attribute	values
Sex (Nominal)	Male—I or female—O
Age (continuous)	Age or patient in the whole number
Education (continuous)	Values—I 4 _____, Some High School—I _____, High School Or G ED=2. College Or Vocational School = 3 _____, college=4
Current Smoker (Nominal)	Yes=1 or No=0
Cigarettes per day (Continuous)	number of cigarettes smoked per day
BP Meds (Nominal)	Yes=1 or No=0 was BP patient or not
Prevalent Stroke (Nominal)	Yes=I or No = 0 Was Stroke patient or not
prevalent Hyp (Nominal)	Yes=I or No = 0 <u>Was whether</u> the patient was hyper sensitive.
Diabetes (Nominal)	Yes=I or No = 0 Was or he a diabetes patient or not
Tot Choi (Continuous)	Total cholesterol level
Sys BP (Continuous)	Systolic Blood pressure
Dia BP (Continuous)	Diastolic Blood
BMI (Continuous)	Body Mass Index
Heart rate (Continuous)	Heart rate or pulse rate
Glucose level (Continuous)	Glucose Level
Ten-year (Nominal) (Target Attribute)	No=2. the 10-year risk Of Coronary Heart Disease (C HD)

TOOLS AND TECHNOLOGIES

Python is used for exploratory investigation and data processing [41]. The following table summarises the libraries that were consulted during this investigation. The 'Pandas' package is used to evaluate data that contains missing values and outliers. For data visualisation and graphing, 'Seaborn' and 'matplotlib' are utilised, which aids in data preparation. We utilised the 'imblearn' package to balance the dataset. The identification of pertinent characteristics and application of classification methods were made feasible with the usage of the 'sklearn'

package. Numpy makes it easier to work with high-level mathematical functions. We used this library to calculate the model's accuracy in our research.

Table 3: Libraries used for Implementation

Library	Purpose
Pandas	Data manipulation and analysis [42]
Numpy	Hi II-level mathematical functions
Seaborn	Data visualization and graph [43]
matplotlib	Plotting
SKlearn	Classification Algorithms
imblearn	SMOTE

Experimentation with Classification by Ensemble (EXAMINATION)

Ensemble learning is a method for improving the accuracy of machine learning outcomes by combining many methods. When it comes to medical research, Ensemble has shown to be a valuable tool for increasing accuracy [48]. As an alternative, this is what we recommend: By merging Logistic Regression and Decision tree approaches, our new Hybrid Dc-IG Algorithm classifies. This ensemble's predictions are 99.1% accurate. This indicates that the model learns from its mistakes in the past to improve its accuracy going forward. We used a boosting method in the ensemble.

Experimentation with Various Classifiers

We also tried with many additional classifiers to illustrate the enhanced accuracy of our proposed ensemble. It is critical to emphasise that all experimental setups and characteristics remained constant. Fig. 6 compares the results achieved using the proposed ensemble with those obtained using a variety of different classifiers of machine learning on the identical features of Framingham dataset.

1) Experimentation Using Logistic Regression:

If you use Logistic Regression in a manner of binary classifier [49], every specimen is divided in two distinct categories either no or yes. It is employed to make predictions about a categorical dependent variable determined by a number of independent variables. A Logistic Regression Model with such a precision of 81% was utilised upon the provided features that are special.

2) Experimentation That Uses KNN

In supervised learning, K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN) actually is a simple parametric approach to utilise. Supervised learning utilises pre-labeled practise data to help guide the learning process. An untrained model predicts a previously known sample when one is encountered. The KNN algorithm performs wonderfully with bigger datasets [51]. In addition, the findings

for numeric characteristics are outstanding. We find out how far apart the k nearest neighbours are by calculating the value of 'k'. The Euclidean Distance is frequently employed for comparing the distances of two neighbours. The Manhattan and Minkowski Distances, on the other hand, may be used to estimate how close two points are to one another. Numeric attributes are found in 4240 of the dataset's occurrences in the Framingham study. The value of k has been set to 5. This method is 83.4 percent accurate.

3) Experimentation Using Decision Tree:

The decision tree algorithm is a subset of the supervised learning family of algorithms. It may be used for classification as well as regression. It creates a tree with a root node that represents the primary attribute. Subsets of the datasets are available. Each subset must be constructed in such a way that at least one of the subset's data point attributes has the same value. This subset is used to create an internal node. The branch reflects the result of the previous node, which leads to the subsequent node. The class is represented by the leaf node.

The advantages are numerous, particular, simple to use, and adaptable. The downsides include the fact that tree structures are susceptible to sampling and tree splitting is hungry. The decision tree is a non-trivial problem. .

Table 4: Comparison

Technique	Limitations	Advantages	Acc%
HD diagnosis using ML classifiers	The Proposed method accuracy is very low.	Computationally less complex.	77
MLP+SVM	Computationally complex.	The performance of the proposed method is high in terms Of prediction accuracy.	80.41
ANN + Fuzzy Logic	More execution time required to generate results.	Accuracy is high.	87.4
ANN ensemble based diagnosis system	Computationally complex.	High accuracy.	89.01
HD diagnosis system based on NB, DT and ANN	The NB and DT performance are LOW.	ANN achieved high performance in term Of accuracy	88.12
Three phase technique based on ANN	High computation time.	High accuracy.	88.89
ANN-FUZZY-AHP	Computationally complex	Achieved high accuracy.	91.1
Relief-Rough set based method for HD detection	Computation time is high.	High accuracy due to selection of appropriate feature for training and testing Of the model.	92.32
Hybrid ML method	LOW accuracy.	LOW computation time.	88.07

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

Missing values are dealt with in the first step of the Hybrid Dc-IG Algorithm by using the mean replacement strategy. The Oversampling Technique is used to correct data imbalance in the second stage. The feature significance approach is used to pick features in the third stage. Python is used to implement our Hybrid Dc-IG Algorithm, which is available on our GitHub repository. The datasets namely the three benchmark datasets are - Framingham, Cleveland and Heart Disease, were used to verify the Hybrid Dc-IG Algorithm, with accuracies of 90 percent respectively. It is clear from the comparison that our Hybrid Dc-IG Algorithm is more accurate than other methods, even though it makes use of less data and uses less computing power. Due to its high reliability, the Hybrid Dc-IG Algorithm may be utilised in the real world to diagnose cardiovascular problems early.

This Hybrid Dc-IG Algorithm's preparation steps increase data dependability by identifying outliers, eliminating noise, and handling missing values. It's important to balance the data thereafter to prevent an incorrect fit to the model. The model's computational complexity is reduced during the feature selection stage. Together, all of these steps improve the algorithm's ability to accurately classify objects. Based on the results of three benchmark datasets, the proposed Hybrid Dc-IG Algorithm is both creative and trustworthy. It leverages a novel ensemble while also combining unique pre-processing and feature selection algorithms. Our new Hybrid Dc-IG Algorithm not only enhances accuracy, but it can also be used consistently to a wide range of datasets for the forecasting disease related to heart and its related tissues. Currently, our new Hybrid Dc-IG Algorithm is being tested on the most recent and most advanced datasets. The Hybrid Dc-IG Algorithm we developed in collaboration with many hospitals is already being tested in real-world settings. So, our innovative Hybrid Dc-IG Algorithm's real-time evaluation of various patients will be revealed in the future, we expect.

REFERENCES

1. S. Ambekar and R. Phalnikar, "Disease risk prediction by using convolutional neural network," in Proc. 4th Int. Conf. Comput. Commun. Control Autom. (ICCUBEA), Aug. 2018, pp. 1–5.
2. Health Stats 2017 by World Health Organization (WHO). Accessed: Mar. 2021. [Online]. Available: [https://www.who.int/news-room/factsheets/detail/cardiovascular-diseases-\(CVDs\)](https://www.who.int/news-room/factsheets/detail/cardiovascular-diseases-(CVDs))
3. D. Mousa, N. Zayed, and I. A. Yassine, "Automatic cardiac MRI localization method," in Proc. Cairo Int. Biomed. Eng. Conf. (CIBEC), Giza, Egypt, Dec. 2014, pp. 153–157.
4. L.-N. Pu, Z. Zhao, and Y.-T. Zhang, "Investigation on cardiovascular risk prediction using genetic information," IEEE Trans. Inf. Technol. Biomed., vol. 16, no. 5, pp. 795–808, Sep. 2012.
5. V. Gil-Guillen, D. Orozco-Beltran, A. Maiques-Galan, J. Aznar-Vicente, J. Navarro, L. Cea-Calvo, F. Quirze-Andrés, J. Redon, and J. Merino-Sanchez, "Agreement between REGICOR and SCORE scales in identifying high cardiovascular risk in the Spanish population," Revista Espanola de Cardiol., vol. 60, no. 10, p. 1042, 2007.
6. A. Khandoker, Y. Al Zaabi, and H. Jelinek, "What can tone and entropy tell us about risk of cardiovascular diseases?" in Proc. Comput. Cardiology Conf. (CinC), Dec. 2019, pp. 1–4.
7. G. Assmann, P. Cullen, and H. Schulte, "Simple scoring scheme for

13. calculating the risk of acute coronary events based on the 10-year follow-up of the prospective cardiovascular Munster (PROCAM) study,” *Circulation*, vol. 105, no. 3, pp. 310–315, 2002.
14. S. K. Jain and B. Bhaumik, “An ultra low power ECG signal processor
15. design for cardiovascular disease detection,” in *Proc. 37th Annu. Int. Conf. IEEE Eng. Med. Biol. Soc. (EMBC)*, Aug. 2015, pp. 857–860.
16. C. Martin-Isla, V. M. Campello, C. Izquierdo, Z. Raisi-Estabragh,
17. B. Baeßler, S. E. Petersen, and K. Lekadir, “Image-based cardiac diagnosis with machine learning: A review,” *Frontiers Cardiovascular Med.*, vol. 7, p. 1, Jan. 2020.
18. R. K. Sevakula, W. T. M. Au-Yeung, J. P. Singh, E. K. Heist,
19. E. M. Isselbacher, and A. A. Armoundas, “State-of-the-Art machine learning techniques aiming to improve patient outcomes pertaining to the cardiovascular system,” *J. Amer. Heart Assoc.*, vol. 9, no. 4, 2020, Art. no. e013924.
20. M.Akhiljabbar, Dr.PritiChandrab, Dr.B.LDeekshatuluc.: "Heart Disease Prediction System using Associative Classification and Genetic Algorithm", ICECIT, (2012)
21. Syed Umar Amin, Kavita Agarwal, Dr. Rizwan Beg.: "Genetic Neural Network Based Data Mining in Prediction of Heart Disease Using Risk Factors", ICT, (2013)
22. BhuvanewariAmma N.G., .: "Cardiovascular Disease Prediction System using Genetic Algorithm and Neural Network", IEEE, 2012
23. Oluwarotimi Williams Samuel, Grace MojisolaAsogbona, Arun Kumar Sangaiahc, Peng Fanga, and Guanglin Lia.: "An Integrated Decision Support System Based on ANN and Fuzzy_AHP for Heart Failure Risk Prediction", SIAT, CAS, (2016)
24. Aditi Gavhane ; GouthamiKokkula ; Isha Pandya ; Prof. Kailas Devadkar.: "Prediction of Heart Disease using Machine Learning", ICECA(2019)
25. K. Mathan, PriyanMalarvizhi Kumar, ParthasarathyPanchatcharam, GunasekaranManogaran, R. Varadharajan.: "A novel Gini index decision tree data mining method with neural network classifiers for prediction of heart disease", Kluwer Academic Publishers Norwell, vol. 22, (2018)
26. Nilakshi P. Waghulde, Nilima P. Patil.: "Genetic Neural Approach for Heart Disease Prediction", ISSN, vol. 4, no. 3, sep-2014
27. Ismail Babaoglu, Omer KaanBaykan, NazifAygul, KurtulusOzdemir, Mehmet Bayrak.: "Assessment of exercise stress testing with artificial neural networkin determining coronary artery disease and predicting lesion localization", Science Direct, 2009
28. William G. Bat.: "Use of an Artificial Neural Network for Data Analysis in Clinical Decision-Making: The Diagnosis of Acute Coronary Occlusio", MITP, vol. 2, issue. 4, 1990
29. Himanshu Sharma, M A Rizvi. : “Prediction of Heart Disease using Machine Learning Algorithms: A Survey ”, International Journal on Recent and Innovation Trends in Computing and Communication, Volume: 5 Issue: 8 , 2017.
30. Jae-Hong Eom, Sung-Chun Kim, Byoung-Tak Zhang.: "AptaCDSS-E: A classifier ensemble-based clinical decision support system for cardiovascular disease level prediction,
31. ScienceDirect", 2008
32. Indira S. FalDessai.: "Intelligent Heart Disease Prediction System Using Probabilistic Neural Network", IJACTE, vol. 2, issue. 3, 2013
33. H.Jayasree, D. S. S. K. R. T. Naren, K. Sai Sankeerth, T. Kumidini.: "HEART DISEASE PREDICTION SYSTEM", www.researchgate.net/publication/334612815, July 2019
34. AH Chen, SY Huang, PS Hong, CH Cheng, EJ Lin.: "HDPS: Heart Disease Prediction System", IEEE, 2011
35. LathaParthiban and R.Subramanian.: "Intelligent Heart Disease Prediction System using CANFIS and Genetic Algorithm", International Journal of Medical and Health Sciences, Vol. 1, No. 5, 2007
36. Jaekwon Kim, Jongsik Lee, Youngho Lee.: "Data-Mining-Based Coronary Heart Disease Risk Prediction Model Using Fuzzy Logic and Decision Tree", Health Inform Research, July 2015
37. V. Krishnaiah, G. Narsimha, and N. Subhash Chandra.: "Heart Disease Prediction System Using Data Mining Technique by Fuzzy K-NN Approach", Springer International Publishing, vol. 1, 2015

38. PriyanMalarvizhi Kumar, S.Lokesh, R.Varatharajan, C.Gokulnath, P.Parthasarathy.: "Cloud and IoT based Disease Prediction and Diagnosis System for Healthcare using Fuzzy Neural Classifier", Future Generation Computer Systems, vol. 86, 2018
39. Richard P. Lippmann and David M. Shahian.: "Coronary Artery Bypass Risk Prediction Using Neural Networks", The Society of Thoracic Surgeons, 1997
40. Bert A. Mobley, Eliot Schechter, William E. Moore, Patrick A. McKee, June E. Eichner.: "Predictions of coronary artery stenosis by artificial neural network", www.elsevier.com, 1999
41. S. Muthukaruppan, M.J. Er.: "A hybrid particle swarm optimization based fuzzy expert system for the diagnosis of coronary artery disease", www.elsevier.com/locate/eswa, 2012
42. G. Thippa Reddy and NeeluKhare.: "An Efficient System for Heart Disease Prediction using Hybrid OFBAT with Rule-Based Fuzzy Logic Model", World Scientific Publishing Company, Vol. 26, No. 4, 2017
43. Jayshril S. Sonawane, D.R. Patil.: "Prediction of Heart Disease Using Multilayer Perceptron Neural Network", ICICES, 2014
44. Miss. Chaitrali S. Dangare, Dr. Mrs. Sulabha S. Apte.: "A DATA MINING APPROACH FOR PREDICTION OF HEART DISEASE USING NEURAL NETWORKS", IJCET, vol. 3, no. 3, 2012
45. Zi-Hui Tang, Juanmei Liu, Fangfang Zeng, Zhongtao Li, Xiaoling Yu, LinuoZho.: "Comparison of Prediction Model for Cardiovascular Autonomic Dysfunction Using Artificial Neural Network and Logistic Regression Analysis", PLOS ONE, vol. 8, no. 8, 2013
46. Yanwei Xing, Jie Wang, Zjijong, Yonghong Gao.: "Combination Data Mining Methods with New Medical Data to Predicting Outcome of Coronary Heart Disease", IEEE, 2007
47. Santhana Krishnan. J, Geetha. S.: "Prediction of Heart Disease Using Machine Learning Algorithms", IEEE, 2019
48. C. Kalaiselvi.: "Diagnosing of heart diseases using average k-nearest neighbor algorithm of data mining", IEEE, 2016
49. Han C. W. Hsiao, Sean H. F. Chen, Jeffrey J. P.: "Deep Learning for Risk Analysis of Specific Cardiovascular Diseases Using Environmental Data and Outpatient Records", IEEE, 2016
50. SoodehNikan, FemidaGwadry-Sridhar, Michael Bauer.: "Machine Learning Application to Predict the Risk of Coronary Artery Atherosclerosis", IEEE, 2016
51. Georgia SpiridonKaranasiou, EvanthiaEleftheriosTripoliti, TheofilosGrigorios Papadopoulos, Fanis Georgios Kalatzis, YorgosGoletsis, Katerina Kyriakos Naka, ArisBechlioulis, AbdelhamidErrachid, DimitriousIoannis Fotiadis.: "Predicting adherence of patients with HF through machine learning techniques", IET, vol. 3, issue 3, 2016
52. Gaurav Dangi, TanupriyaChoudhary, Praveen Kumar.: "A smart approach to diagnose Heart disease through machine learning and Springleaf Marketing Response", IEEE, 2016
53. IEEE, 2016
54. Jagdeep Singh, Amit Kamra, Harbhahg Singh.: "Prediction of heart diseases using associative classification", IEEE, 2016
55. SeyedaminPouriyeh, Sara Vahid, Giovanna Sannino, Giuseppe De Pietro, Hamid Arabnia, Juan Gutierrez.: "A comprehensive investigation and comparison of Machine Learning Techniques in the domain of heart disease", IEEE, 2017
56. Yang Peilli, Yin Xuezheng, Ye Jian, Yang Lingfeng, Zhao Hui, Liang Jimin.: "Deep learning model management for coronary heart disease early warning research", IEEE, 2018
57. G. Shanmugasundaram, V. Malar Selvam, R. Saravanan, S.Balaji.: "An Investigation of Heart Disease Prediction Techniques", IEEE, 2018
58. SnehaBorkar, M. N. Annadate.: "Supervised Machine Learning Algorithm for Detection of Cardiac Disorders", IEEE, 2018
59. SanchayitaDhar, Krishna Roy, TanureeDey, Pritha, Datta, Ankur Biswas.: "A Hybrid Machine Learning Approach for Prediction of Heart Diseases", IEEE, 2018
60. Md. Razu Ahmed, S M Hasan Mahmud, Md. AltabHossin, Hosney Jahan, ShekRashedHaiderNoori.: "A Cloud Based Four-Tier Architecture for Early Detection of Heart Disease with Machine Learning

- Algorithms", IEEE, 2018
61. Laiqat Ali, AwaisNiamat, Javed Ali Khan, Noorbakhs mamiriGolilarz, XiongXingzhong, Adeeb Noor, RedhwanNour, Syed Ahmad Chan Bukhari.: "An Optimized Stacked Support Vector Machines Based Expert System for the Effective Prediction of Heart Failure", IEEE, vol. 7, 2019
 62. Senthilkumar Mohan, ChandrasegarThirumalai, Gautam Srivastava.: "Effective Heart Disease Prediction Using Hybrid Machine Learning Techniques", IEEE, vol. 7, 2019
 63. Frantisek Babic, Jaroslav Olejar, Zuzana Vantova, Jan Paralic.: "Predictive and descriptive analysis for heart disease diagnosis", IEEE, 2017
 64. Juan Jose Beunza, Enrique Puertas, Ester Garcia Ovejero, GemaVillalba, Emilia Condes, GerganaKoleva, Cristian Hurtado, Manuel F. Landecho.: "Comparison of machine learning algorithms for clinical event prediction (risk of coronary heart disease)", Journal Of Biomedical Informatics, vol. 97, 2019
 65. C. Beulah ChristalinLatha, S. CarolinJeeva.: "Improving the accuracy of prediction of heart disease risk based on ensemble classification techniques", Informatics in Medicine Unlocked, vol.16, 2019
 66. SamanehLayeghianJavan, Mohammad Mehdi Sepehri, Hassan Aghajani.: "Toward analyzing and synthesizing previous research in early prediction of cardiac arrest using machine learning based on a multi-layered integrative Hybrid Dc-IG Algorithm ", Journal Of Biomedical Informatics, vol. 88, page 70-89, 2018
 67. EvanthiaTripoliti, Theofilos G. Papadopoulos, Georgia, S. Karansiou, Katerina K. Naka.: "Heart Failure: Diagnosis, Severity Estimation And Prediction Of Adverse Events Through Machine Learning Techniques", Computational and Structural Biotechnology Journal, 2016
 68. Ashok kumarDwivedi, "Evaluate the performance of different machine learning techniques for prediction of heart disease using ten-fold cross-validation", Springer, 17 September 2016.
 69. Mythili T, Dev Mukherji, Nikita Padalia, and Abhiram Naidu.: "A Heart Disease Prediction Model using SVM-Decision Trees-Logistic Regression (SDL)", International Journal of Computer Applications , vol. 68, no. 16, 2013
 70. Bashar Brahmi, Mirsaeid Hosseini Shirvani, "Prediction and Diagnosis of Heart Disease by Data Mining Techniques", Journals of Multidisciplinary Engineering Science and Technology, vol.2, 2 February 2015, pp.164168.
 71. SairabiH.Mujawar, P.R.Devale, "Prediction of Heart Disease using Modified K- means and by using Naïve Bayes", International Journal of Innovative research in Computer and Communication Engineering, vol.3, October 2015, pp.10265-10273.
 72. NouraAjam, "Heart Disease Diagnoses using Artificial Neural Network", The International Insitute of Science, Technology and Education, vol.5, No.4, 2015, pp.7-11.
 73. S.Prabhavathi, D.M.Chitra, "Analysis and Prediction of Various Heart Diseases using DNFS Techniques", International Journal of Innovations in Scientific and Engineering Research, vol.2, 1, January 2016, pp.1-7.
 74. Jayami Patel, Prof. TejalUpadhay, Dr. Samir Patel, "Heart disease Prediction using Machine Learning and Data mining Technique", March 2017.